

The Influence of Social Media Marketing Instagram and Brand Engagement on Brand Loyalty at Oentukmu Artisan Cake Malang City

Adista Ayunda Sari¹, Fullchis Nurtjahjani², Yulis Nurul Aini³

^{1,2,3}Marketing Management, Department of Business Administration, State Polytechnic of Malang

¹adista615@gmail.com, ²fullchis@polinema.ac.id, ³yulisenurulai@polinema.ac.id

Article DOI: 10.55677/SSHRB/2025-3050-0705

DOI URL: <https://doi.org/10.55677/SSHRB/2025-3050-0705>

KEYWORDS: Social Media Marketing, Brand Engagement, Brand Loyalty.

ABSTRACT: This study analyzes the influence of Social Media Marketing Instagram and brand engagement on brand loyalty at Oentukmu Artisan Cake Malang City. A quantitative approach was used with data collected from 96 respondents through an offline questionnaire using purposive sampling. Data were analyzed using multiple linear regression and hypothesis testing. Descriptive results show that respondents generally agree or strongly agree with the statements proposed. The classical assumption test shows that the data meets the requirements of normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity. The coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.821 indicates that 82,1% of the variation in brand loyalty can be explained by the independent variables, while 17,9% is influenced by other factors. The t-test shows that social media marketing on ($t = 4.557$ sig. 0.000) and brand engagement ($t = 4.679$, sig. 0.000) have a significant effect partially. The F test shows a significant effect simultaneously ($F = 96.344$, sig. 0.000). This study concludes that there is an influence between social media marketing and brand engagement on brand loyalty at Oentukmu Artisan Cake Malang City. Therefore, it is recommended that Oentukmu Artisan Cake needs to improve interaction and good communication and create more interactive content.

Corresponding Author:

Adista Ayunda Sari

Published: July 04, 2025

License: This is an open access article under the CC BY 4.0 license:

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

INTRODUCTION

The food and beverage (F&B) industry is one of the fastest growing business sectors worldwide, including in Indonesia. This growth is driven by lifestyle changes, urbanization, and increasing public awareness of the importance of food and beverage quality. Food and beverage consumption is not only a basic need, but also part of a modern lifestyle that encourages innovation and differentiation in products and services. Various segments in the F&B industry, ranging from fast food, premium restaurants, to healthy and environmentally friendly food, show great potential to continue to grow.

Oentukmu is one of the cake companies in Malang established in 2020, the business is known for its fresh Korean flower cakes and Asian-inspired flavors. It is also famous for incorporating art into cakes through intricate attention to detail and meticulous flower arrangements. Observations at oentukmu in 2024 show that sales performance is increasing but engagement on social media, namely Instagram, is decreasing. This decline is believed to stem from negative

engagement and not maximizing social media marketing, especially in content creation and interaction with consumers. One of the key factors that influence brand loyalty is social media marketing. This shows that people will remember the brand more if the brand appears frequently on their social media, for example through content. According to (Truten and Wimsatt, 2020) Social media marketing is the use of social media to create, communicate, deliver and exchange offers that have value for companies and stakeholders. Empirical studies conducted by Abrar Fajar Ramadhan (2019), and Alfian Dally Irawan and Aswin Dewanto (2020) confirm that social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on brand loyalty. Therefore, when consumers see content or how to promote brands more often through social media, consumers will tend to remember the brand more.

In addition, brand engagement plays a strategic role in influencing brand loyalty, especially for baking products that require product references. According to Sarmad (2020) Brand engagement is the level of consumer personal motivation, which is related to the brand and context-related

thinking characterized by certain stages, namely cognitive, emotional, and behavioral directly interacting with the brand. Supporting this, research by Ganawati and Arwini Sumardi (2021) and Riza Khusniah et al (2024) found that brand engagement has a positive and significant effect on brand loyalty. communicative interaction, can help foster trust and establish a closer relationship between companies and consumers.

Based on the above background, this study aims to examine the influence of social media marketing Instagram and brand engagement on brand loyalty at Oentukmu Artisan Cake in Malang. This research also seeks to provide input to develop marketing strategies that are more effective and responsive to consumers, especially in the face of increasingly fierce competition in markets that rely on social media.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Marketing

According to Kotler & Armstrong (2023: 2) marketing is a social and managerial process that makes individuals and groups get what they need and want through the creation and mutual exchange of products and values with others. Another opinion is also expressed by Tjiptono and Diana (2020: 3), marketing is the process of creating, distributing, promoting, and pricing goods, services and ideas to facilitate satisfying exchange relationships with customers and to build and maintain positive relationships with stakeholders in a dynamic environment

Marketing Management

According to Kotler and Keller (2022), marketing management is considered the art and science of attracting, retaining and increasing customers by defining target markets and making superior customer value. Another opinion by Sudarsono (2020), marketing management is the process of planning, implementing (which includes organizing, directing, and coordinating) marketing operations within the company to achieve organizational goals efficiently and effectively.

Brand Loyalty

According to (Kotler, P., & Keller, 2019) loyalty is a deep commitment to buy or support a product again, even if contextual influences and marketing efforts have the potential to lead to customer conversion. As for the indicators of brand loyalty, namely: 1) repeat purchase, 2) brand preference, 3) price resistance, 4) brand recommendation, 5) emotional commitment

Social Media Marketing

Truten and Wimsatt, (2020) Social media marketing is the use of social media to create, communicate, deliver and exchange offers that have value for companies and their stakeholders. According to Chen and Lin in (2019) there are five dimensions that are used as effective variables in the use of social media marketing, as follows: 1) Entertainment, 2)

Interaction, 3) Customization, 4.) Trendiness, 5.) Word of mouth.

Instagram

Instagram comes from the word “instant” or ‘insta’, like the polaroid cameras that used to be better known as “instant photos”. There are different opinions about the meaning of Instagram, according to Ratnasari, et al. (2021:31), "Instagram is a completely visual platform. Unlike facebook which relies on text and images, or twitter which only relies on text, instagram's sole purpose is to allow its users to share images or videos with their audience". Meanwhile, Hutahaean, et al. (2022: 7), explains that “Instagram is a social networking platform that allows its users to take photos, edit, apply digital filters, and upload them with various features, such as comment columns, and DM or direct message features that allow users to exchange messages”.

Brand Engagement

According to Sarmad (2020) Brand engagement is the level of personal motivation of consumers, which is related to brands and context-related thinking characterized by certain stages, namely cognitive, emotional, and behavioral directly interacting with the brand. Hollebeek (2020) provides an understanding that Brand Engagement is a cognitive, emotional, and behavioral activity that is positively related to a brand for consumers; consumers will be bound through interactions with the brand for a certain period of time.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research was conducted at Oentukmu Artisan Cake Malang City, focusing on the social media marketing instagram, brand engagement and brand loyalty on customer customers make at least 2 purchases. The object of this research consists of three variables: brand loyalty as the dependent variable (Y), and social media marketing (X1) and brand engagement (X2) as independent variables. The population in this study includes consumers who have 2 purchases at Oentukmu Artisan Cake Malang City during the period from Juni to December 2024. A total of 96 respondents were selected using a non-probability sampling technique, specifically purposive sampling.

This study adopts a quantitative research design. Primary data were collected through offline questionnaires distributed directly to respondents. The measurement instruments were based on indicators derived from relevant theories, including those by Chen dan Lin for social media marketing, Hollebeek for brand engagement, and Kotler and Keller for brand loyalty. To ensure the validity and reliability of the data, the study included validity and reliability tests for the research instrument. The data analysis consisted of several stages: descriptive statistical analysis, classical assumption tests (normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity), multiple linear regression analysis, and hypothesis testing using both t-test (partial) and F-test (simultaneous). The coefficient of determination (R^2) was

also calculated to determine the proportion of variance in purchase decisions explained by the independent variables.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Research result

Validity Test

Table 1 Validity Test Results

Variabel	Item	rhitung	rtabel	Sig.	Taraf Sig.	Keterangan
<i>Social Media Marketing (X1)</i>	X1.1	0,711	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.2	0,688	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.3	0,673	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.4	0,698	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.5	0,768	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.6	0,722	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.7	0,714	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.8	0,776	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.9	0,626	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.10	0,768	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
<i>Brand Engagement (X2)</i>	X2.1	0,664	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.2	0,715	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.3	0,659	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.4	0,807	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.5	0,569	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.6	0,780	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
<i>Brand Loyaty (Y)</i>	Y1.1	0,743	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.2	0,657	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.3	0,721	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.4	0,754	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.5	0,659	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.6	0,558	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.7	0,727	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.8	0,607	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.9	0,665	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.10	0,624	0,167	0,000	0,05	Valid

Reliability Test

Table 2. Reliability Test Result

Variabel	Cronbach Alpha	Standar	Keterangan
<i>Social Media Marketing (X1)</i>	0,771	0,70	Reliabel
<i>Brand Engagement (X2)</i>	0,888	0,70	Reliabel
Brand Loyalty (Y)	0,942	0,70	Reliabel

Source: Processed data (2025).

Based on the table above, the reliability test results show that all variables have a Cronbach alpha value of more than 0.6. This shows that the items of the Social Media Marketing (X1), Brand Engagement (X2), and Brand Loyalty (Y) variables are considered reliable and reliable as variable measuring instruments in research.

Analysis Deskriptif

Table 3. Descriptive Social Media Marketing Variables.

Indicator	Item	Rata-Rata Jawaban Responden					Mean
		STS (1)	TS (2)	N (3)	S (4)	SS (5)	
Entertainment X1.1	1. Entertainment	1	3	15	42	35	4,11
	2. Creative interaction	0	1	16	38	41	4,23
Mean Entertainment							4,17
Interaction X1.2	3. Reciprocity	0	5	21	30	40	4,09
	4. Participatory	3	10	21	35	27	3,76
Mean Interaction							3,92
Trendiness X1.3	5. Popular formats	0	2	18	32	44	4,22
	6. Hot topics	1	2	16	40	36	4,11
Mean Trendiness							4,16
Customization X1.4	7. Content as needed	1	8	19	37	31	3,92
	8. Campaigns	1	7	16	35	37	4,04
Mean Customization							3,98
Word of Mouth X1.5	9. Testimonial	1	1	8	35	51	4,39
	10. Viral content	1	1	9	34	51	4,38
Mean Word of Mouth							4,38
Mean Social Media Marketing (X1)							4,13

Table 4. Descriptive Brand Engagement Variables.

Indicator	Item	Rata-Rata Jawaban Responden					Mean
		STS (1)	TS (2)	N (3)	S (4)	SS (5)	
Cognitive X2.1	1. Brand communication	3	3	16	41	33	4,02
	2. Interactive media	1	1	12	44	38	4,21
Mean Cognitionif							4,11
Emotional X2.2	3. Visual	0	2	9	36	49	4,37
	4. Social engagement	3	12	15	32	34	3,85
Mean Emotional							4,11
Interactive X2.3	5. Educational	0	1	12	41	42	4,29
	6. Collaborative	4	4	26	32	30	3,83
Mean Interactive							4,06
Mean Brand Engagement(X2)							4,09

Table 5. Descriptive Brand Loyalty Variables.

Indicator	Item	Rata-Rata Jawaban Responden					Mean
		STS (1)	TS (2)	N (3)	S (4)	SS (5)	
Repeat Purchase Y1	1.Desire to buy	1	3	15	37	40	4,16
	2.Brand Loyalty	4	10	23	36	23	3,66
Mean Repeat Purchase							3,91
Brand Preferences Y2	3. Choice of a particular brand	1	10	23	34	28	3,81
	4. Bound to the brand	0	2	20	28	26	4,12
Mean Brand Preferences							3,65
Price Resistance Y3	5. Willingness to keep buying	0	3	14	47	32	4,12
	6. Reaction to discounts/promotions	0	0	13	44	39	4,27
Mean Price Resistance							4,19
Brand Recommendation Y4	7. Recommend	0	0	18	34	44	4,27
	8. Satisfied with the brand	0	1	19	34	42	4,21
Mean Brand Recommendation							4,24
Emotional Commitment Y5	9.esistant to criticism/suggestions	04	17	36	39		4,14
	10. Believes in the brand	1	1	12	35	47	4,31
Mean Emotional Commitment							4,22
Mean Brand Loyalty (X1)							4,11

Classical Assumption Test

Normality Test

Based on the results of testing the normality test using the normality probability plot, the effect of social media marketing and brand engagement on brand loyalty with the basis for decision making in the normality test, namely if the data spreads around the diagonal line and follows the direction of the diagonal line or the histogram graph shows a normal distribution pattern, then the normality test results of this regression model fulfill the normality assumption.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 7. Multicollinearity Test Results

Model	Collinerarity		Keterangan
	Tolerance	VIF	
Social Media Marketing (X1)	0,394	2,540	No multicollinearity
Brand Engagement (X2)	0,394	2,540	No multicollinearity

Source: Processed data (2025).

Based on the table above, the results of the multicollinearity test can be seen that the VIF value of the social media marketing and product innovation variables has a tolerance of 0.10 and VIF < 10, thus the independent variables can be said not to occur multicollinearity.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Based on the picture above, the results of the heteroscedasticity test can be seen that the points spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis, it can be concluded that this regression model does not occur heteroscedasticity.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Table 7. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test Results

Coefficients ^a						Collinearity		
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
		B	Std. Error	Beta				
1	(Constant)	8.907	2.346	8.907	1.661	0.05		
	Social Media Marketing	.389	.085	.389	4.557	0.05	0.394	2.540
	Brand Engagement	.656	.140	.656	4.679	0.05	0.394	2.540

a. Dependent Variable: Brand Loyalty

Source : Processed data (2025).

Based on the results of the multiple linear regression analysis test in the table above, a multiple linear regression model equation can be seen as follows :

$$Y = 8,907 + 0,389 X1 + 0,656 X2 + e$$

The multiple linear regression equation shows the direction of influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable. The explanation of the multiple linear regression equation is as follows :

1. Constant Value (a) = 8.907
The constant value of 8.907 means that if all independent variables, namely social media marketing (X1) and brand engagement (X2) are ignored or assumed to be 0 (zero), then the brand loyalty variable (Y) will be equal to its constant value of 0.907.
2. Social Media Marketing Variable Regression Coefficient (b1) = 0.389
The multiple regression coefficient value of social media marketing (X1) of 0.389 is positive. This means that if there is an increase in value by 1 unit in the social media marketing variable and the brand engagement variable is assumed to be 0 (zero), then brand loyalty (Y) will increase by 0.389.
3. Regression Coefficient Value Brand engagement variable (b2) = 0.656
The multiple regression coefficient value of brand engagement (X2) of 0.656 is positive. This means that if there is an increase in value by 1 unit in the brand engagement variable and the social media marketing variable is assumed to be 0 (zero), the brand loyalty variable (Y) will increase by 0.656.

Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis, the social media marketing (X1) and brand engagement (X2) variables that have the greatest contribution or effect on brand loyalty (Y) are brand engagement (X2) with a coefficient of 0.656 compared to social media marketing (X1) with a coefficient of 0.389.

F TEST**Table 2: Model Feasibility Test Results (F Test)****ANOVA^a**

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	2087,985	2	1043,993	96,344	,000 ^b
Residual	1007,754	93	10,836		
Total	3095,740	95			

Source : Processed data (2025)

Based on the table above, the significance value is $0.000 < 0.05$. So it can be social media marketing, brand engagement simultaneously have a significant effect on brand loyalty. Thus, the model is considered feasible to test and the hypothesis can be continued.

DISCUSSION

1. The Influence of Social Media Marketing (X1) on Brand Loyalty

Based on the results of the analysis of the description of social media marketing variables, the word of mouth indicator has the highest mean of 4.38. This means that respondents strongly agree with the word of mouth indicator, namely that Oentukmu Artisan Cake has interesting content so that it can create virality and become a conversation such as content reviewing cake products with a korean look.

Based on the partial hypothesis test that has been carried out, it can be seen that the influence of social media marketing on brand loyalty has a positive effect on purchasing decisions. This result is evidenced by the t test results, namely $t_{count} > t_{table}$, namely $4.557 > 1.661$ and significant $0.000 < 0.05$. The results of this study are in accordance with the hypothesis which states that it is suspected that social media marketing has a positive effect on Oentukmu Artisan Cake. This is because in the social media marketing variable there is an item with the largest mean, namely testimonials. The testimonial item has a mean of 4.39 and can be classified in the high mean category. Oentukmu Artisan Cake uses social media marketing in the form of Instagram to promote products by providing interesting content so that it can reach a wider audience and become a good conversation, dominated by women aged 18-23 years with job characteristics as students. This is because the 20s age range is generally active on social media, has a high interest in food trends, especially products that have aesthetic value. In addition, women are also more likely to share their culinary experiences digitally. The ease of finding information on the @oen.tuk.mu account, consumers and potential consumers can choose which products they want to buy according to their needs.

The results of this study support the results of previous research conducted by Alfian et al (2020) entitled The Effect of Social Media Marketing Activities on Brand Trust, Brand Equity, and Brand Loyalty on the Instagram Social Media Platform. The results of this study state that social media marketing has a positive and significant influence on brand loyalty. Based on all the data obtained, it can be stated that social media marketing has a positive effect on purchasing decisions at Oentumu Artisan Cake.

2. The Influence of Brand Engagement (X2) on Brand Loyalty

Based on the results of the analysis of the description of brand engagement variables, the cognitive and emotional indicators have the highest mean of 4.11. This means that on average respondents agree to cognitive indicators, namely respondents feel that Oentukmu Artisan Cake is able to present products with quality ingredients and aesthetic designs, so that they more easily remember and think about it when they want to buy a cake, and emotional indicators, namely respondents feel happy when they see Instagram content from Oentukmu, or feel directly connected through personal communication because they celebrate special moments with friends and family.

Based on partial hypothesis testing that has been carried out, it can be seen that the effect of brand engagement on brand loyalty has a positive effect on brand loyalty. This result is evidenced by the results of the t test, namely $t_{count} > t_{table}$, namely $4.679 > 1.661$ and a significant $0.000 < 0.05$. The results of this study are in accordance with the hypothesis which states that it is suspected that brand engagement has a positive effect on brand loyalty at Oentukmu Artisan Cake. This is because in the brand engagement variable there is an item with the largest mean, namely visual. Visual items have the largest mean of 4.37 and can be classified in the very high mean category. The visuals displayed by Oentukmu, especially with the aesthetic and contemporary Korean look concept, are proven to be able to attract attention, increase audience engagement, and create a strong impression so that it has an impact on consumers with a female dominance of 18-23 years old with job characteristics as students. This is because young people like visual displays that are attractive, unique, and in line with popular trends.

The results of this study support the results of previous research conducted by Rosmalianda Aprilia (2022) entitled Analysis of The Effect of Brand Trust and Brand Engagement on Brand Loyalty Cosmetic Products. The results of this study state that social media marketing has a positive and significant influence on brand loyalty. Based on all the data obtained, it can be stated that brand engagement has a positive effect on purchasing decisions at Oentukmu Artisan Cake.

3. The Influence of Social Media Marketing (X1) and Brand Engagement (X2) on Brand Loyalty

Based on the results of the coefficient of determination analysis, the Adjusted R Square is 0.821 or 82.1%, which means that the contribution of social media marketing and brand engagement to brand loyalty at Oentukmu Artisan Cake is 82.1%, while the remaining 17.9% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study. Based on multiple linear regression analysis, it is known that the variable that has the greatest contribution or effect on brand loyalty is brand engagement with a coefficient of 0.656 compared to social media marketing with a coefficient of 0.389. In this case it can be said that Oentukmu Artisan Cake has very good brand engagement on brand loyalty. Based on the simultaneous hypothesis testing that has been carried out, it can be seen that the effect of social media marketing and brand engagement on brand loyalty has a positive effect, this result is evidenced by the results of the F test, namely $F_{hitung} > F_{tabel}$, namely $96.344 > 3.090$ and a significant $0.000 < 0.05$. The results showed that social media marketing and brand engagement simultaneously had a positive effect on brand loyalty.

RESEARCH CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion, the research results can be concluded as follows:

1. Social media marketing partially has a positive effect on brand loyalty. This means that to increase brand loyalty from consumers, social media marketing is needed which consists of entertainment, interaction, trendiness, customization, and word of mouth.
2. Brand Engagement partially has a positive effect on brand loyalty decisions. This means that to increase brand loyalty, excellent engagement is needed, including cognitive, emotional, and interactive.
3. Social media marketing and brand engagement simultaneously have a positive effect on brand loyalty. This means that to increase brand loyalty it is necessary to have very good social media marketing and brand engagement.

Suggestions

Based on the conclusions obtained, the suggestions that can be conveyed are :

1.) Suggestions for PT Pegadaian (Persero) CP Kota Lama Malang

1. To increase brand loyalty, excellent social media marketing is needed. Oentukmu Artisan Cake should further increase interaction with the audience and even consumers and potential consumers to stay connected with the audience. As well as responding to comments, messages, or questions from the audience and asking interesting questions to the audience to encourage discussion and interaction.
2. To increase brand loyalty brand engagement is good. Oentukmu Artisan Cake should further enhance its engagement strategy to improve the quality of two-way interactions between brands and consumers, both through social media and offline activities. Strategies that can be done include creating content that encourages participation, such as quizzes, polls, and challenges, organizing offline events such as baking classes, cake decorating workshops, or customer community meet-ups, and appreciating loyal customers through membership programs or reward systems
3. In the brand engagement variable (X2), future researchers should consider broad coverage or only limited to social media engagement.

2.) Suggestions for Futher Research

1. Future researchers are advised to add other indicators to make the research results more accurate and should expand the scope of the research area for generalization of research results.
2. It is recommended for future researchers to replace or add other variables.

REFERENCES

1. Khusniah *et al*, 2024, *How Social Media Impacts on Customer Brand Engagement, Brand Trust and Brand Loyalty*, 18(01), 2338-4654.
2. Kotler, Philip and Keller dan Gary Amstrong. (2012). *Principles Of Marketing*. Global Edition. Pearson Education.
3. Aaker, David. (2020). *Ekuitas Merek*. Jakarta: Penerbit Mitra Utama.
4. Alma, Buchari. (2014). *Manajemen Pemasaran dan Pemasaran Jasa*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
5. Aprilia Rosmalinda *et al*, 2022, Analisis Pengaruh *Brand Trust* dan *Brand Engagement* Terhadap *Brand Loyalty* Produk Kosmetik (Survei Pada Wanita Pengguna Produk Kosmetik Maybelline di Kota Sukabumi), 3(4) 1980-1987.
6. Diwyarthi *et al*. 2022. *Perilaku Konsumen*. Tangah: PT. Global Eksekutif Teknologi
7. Ghozali, Imam. (2021). *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
8. Ramadhan & Zuliestina, 2020, Analisis Pemanfaatan Youtube Sebagai Social Media Marketing Go-Jek Dalam Mempengaruhi Minat Beli dan Loyalitas Terhadap Brand, 1(4), 326-338.
9. Sukidy Beatrice dan Achmadi Hendra, 2024. The Effect of Social Media Marketing Activities on Brand Loyalty Witih Brand Image and Brand Awareness as Mediation Variable at XYZ Beauty Clininc in Jakarta, 05(01), 1-9.
10. Wardhana Ali dan Susilawaty, 2020, *The Impact of Consumer-Brand Engagement on Smartphone's Brand Loyalty in Indonesia*, 174, 131-134.